

UGC Approved Journal No – 47168
(IIJIF) Impact Factor - 3.234

ISSN 2231 – 413X

SHODH PRERAK

A Multidisciplinary Quarterly International *Peer Reviewed* Refereed Research
Journal

Chief Editor:

Dr. Shashi Bhushan Poddar

Editors:

Dr. Reeta Yadav

Dr. Pradeep Kumar

Volume 11

Issue II

April

2021

Published By:

Veer Bahadur Seva Sanstha

Lucknow

Printed at:

F/70 South City, Rai Bareilly Road, Lucknow-226025

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Cell NO.: 09415390515, 09450245771, 08960501747

Cite this Volume as S/P, Vol. 11, Issue II, April 2021

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Mental Health as a Function of Some Psycho-Social Predictors

*Prof. (Dr.) Dinesh Kumar**

The study was conducted on 120 male adolescent respondents to examine the association of alienation, locus of control, SES and social support with their mental health. It was hypothesized that : (i) alienation, locus of control, SES and social support all would have significant association with mental health among the adolescent respondents. (ii) alienation, locus of control, SES and social support all will be found significantly related to mental health score. For the purpose, Hindi Adaptation of Dean's Alienation Scale by Singh and Sinha, Hindi version of Rotter's Locus of Control Scale by Singh, R.N., Bhardwaj SES Scale, Social Support Scale by Asthana and Verma, MMHSI by Thakur and Kumar along with PDS were used to measure alienation, locus of control, SES, social support, mental health and to get other relevant information about the respondents respectively. The obtained data were analysed using chi-square and Pearson 'r'. The results upheld hypotheses. It was found that (i) people belonging to low alienation, internal locus of control, high SES and high social support groups manifested comparatively sound mental health than their counterparts (ii) There existed a significant positive correlation of mental health score with locus of control (ILC to ELC), SES & social support respectively but a significant negative correlation with alienation. Thus, it was concluded that psycho-social factors under reference are predictors of mental health.

Introduction

The present study includes four components which need elaboration. The first component of the present study is alienation which refers to a feeling of strangeness or separation from other; a sense of a lack of warm relations with others. Alienation is a dynamic integration of a number of cognition and feelings such as the feeling of isolation of powerlessness of neglect and despair of a vague and blurred vision of identity and of being swept away of the mainstream. Ultimately, it also means a divergence from one's self.

Locus of control refers to an individual's perception of what are the main causes of events in the life. It means a belief about whether the outcome of our actions are contingent on what we do or on events outside our personal control. The factors relating to the belief that our action is a function of our own ability, belief and proficiency are known as internal locus of control. On the other hand the factors relating to the belief that our action is the function of factors outside it are called external locus of control. These are also called internal locus of control and external locus of control.

One component of the present study is social support which refers to the information that lead the individual to believe that he is cared and loved, esteemed, valued that he or she belong to a network of communication and mutual obligation (Cobb, 1976).

Mental health is of great concern of psychologists. Many people, when they hear the mental health, think of mental illness, but mental health is far more than an absence of mental illness. In general mental health refers to the ability to balance, feelings, desires, ambitions and ideals in one's daily life. It means the ability to face and accept the realities of life (Reber et al., 2009).

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Alienation, locus of control, SES and Social Support all are likely to influence the life style, adjustment including mental health of the respondents. Review of literature indicates that various studies have been conducted linking the variables with mental health even in India but without studies linking Bihar. This justifies undertaking of the present study.

Objectives

It was intended to examine the

- association of alienation, locus of control, SES and Social Support with mental health of the respondents.
- relationship of alienation, locus of control, SES and social support with mental health.

Hypotheses

- (i) Alienation, locus of control, SES and social support all will be found significantly associated with mental health of the respondents.
- (ii) Alienation, locus of control, SES and social support all will be found significantly related to mental health.

Method of Study

Sample Used

The study was conducted on purposive sample of 120 selected out of 300 respondents belonging to Patna town equal in respect of high and low alienation ILC & ELC, high and low SES and high and low social support groups respectively. Other than the conditions required for research, they were matched so far as practicable.

Research Tools Used

- A personal Data Sheet was used to get the necessary information relating to the respondents.
- Dean's Alienation Scale adapted in Hindi by Singh & Sinha was used to measure the level or amount of alienation of the respondents.
- Hindi Adaptation of Rotter's Locus of Control Scale by Singh, R.N. was employed on the respondents to measure locus of control of the respondents.
- Bhardwaj SES Scale was employed to measure SES of respondents.
- Social Support Scale by Asthana, Madhu and Verma Kiran Bala was used to measure social support of the respondents.
- MMHSI by Thakur and Kumar was used to measure mental health status of response their support all will be found significantly related to mental health.

Results and Interpretations

Table-01

Chi-square showing the association of alienation, locus of control, SES and Social Support with mental health of the respondents.

Variables	Group	N	Mental Health		χ^2	df	P
			Sound	Poor			
Alienation	High	50	29%	71%	29.17	1	<.01
	Low	50	67%	33%			
Locus of Cont.	ELC	50	62%	38%	35.63	1	<.01
	ILC	50	30%	70%			
SES	High	50	68%	32%	23.35	1	<.01
	Low	50	34%	66%			
Soc. Support	High	50	68%	32%	29.17	1	<.01
	Low	50	30%	70%			

The results displayed by table clearly revealed the significant association of alienation with mental health. More than 67% of low alienated group and only 29% of high alienated group manifested sound mental health. On the other hand more than 71% of high alienated group and only 33% of low alienated group manifested poor mental health. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 29.17$, $df = 1$; $p < .01$). The findings might be interpreted on the ground that higher degree of alienation is characterised by stress, anxiety and thereby having poor mental health.

Further, the results displayed in table showed significant association of locus of control with mental health of the respondents. The external locus of control (ELC) group of respondents 62% showed superiority over internal locus of control (ILC) group of respondents 30% in respect of having sound mental health ($\chi^2=35.63$; $df=1$; $P<.01$). The finding might be interpreted in terms of more flexible interaction with the external world on the part of the internal locus of control group of respondents.

Further, high SES group of respondents 68% were found having sound mental health than their low SES 34% counterparts ($\chi^2=23.35$; $df=1$; $P<.01$). The finding might be interpreted on the ground of a series of problems faced by low SES group leading to manifest poor mental health.

Further respondents belonging to high social support group of respondents 68% showed sound mental health than their counterparts 30% belonging to low social support group ($\chi^2=29.17$; $df=1$; $P<.01$). Thus hypothesis no. (1) is fully retained. The finding might be interpreted on the ground of less personal independence and high need structure on the part of respondents of high social support group.

Table-02

r-showing the relationship of alienation, locus of control, SES and social support with mental health

Variables	N	r	df	P
Alienation Vs Mental Health	120	-0.483	118	<.01
Locus of control Vs Mental Health	120	0.479	118	<.01
SES Vs Mental Health	120	0.480	118	<.01
Social Support Vs Mental Health	120	0.475	118	<.01

The results displayed by table-02 clearly revealed the significant positive correlation of mental health with locus of control ($r = 0.479$; $df = 118$; $p < .01$), SES ($r = 0.480$; $df = 118$; $p < .01$), social support ($r = 0.475$; $df = 118$; $p < .01$), but a significant negative correlation with alienation ($r = -0.483$; $df = 118$; $p < .01$). Thus hypothesis no. (2) is retained. The findings are in agreement with the findings of table-(01). The interpretation remained the same.

Conclusions

- (i) Mental health is significantly associated with alienation, LOC, SES and social support. Low alienation, ILC, high SES and high social support all are conducive to sound mental health.
- (ii) A significant positive correlation of mental health existed with locus of control, SES & social support respectively but a significant negative correlation with alienation.

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